

Oxidative stress effect of levofloxacin on broilers

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Abstract

Levofloxacin is a recent broad-spectrum antibiotic indicated in several bacterial diseases in broilers. This study was done to evaluate the oxidative effects in poultry industry. It was carried out on 90 healthy chickens 6 weeks old, classified into 3 major groups 30 in each major group (control groups, levofloxacin 40 mg /kg/day groups and levofloxacin 180 mg /kg/day groups). Each major group then divided into 3 groups (10 chickens in each) for administration on Levofloxacin for one day, three days and five days. The study declared that levofloxacin causes a dose and time dependent oxidative stress in blood, liver, kidney and brain tissues, which revealed significant decrease SOD activity and GSH level in all groups except one day treatment while MDA level increased in serum and whole tissues which indicates increased oxidative stress in broilers.

Keywords: broiler, Levofloxacin, oxidative stress, growth

Introduction

Fluoroquinolones are gaining widespread acceptance in veterinary medicine as they have broad spectrum activity against Gram-negative and Gram positive bacteria, mycoplasma, rickettsia as well as against bacteria resistant to other drugs. (Lenart-Boron *et al.* 2016). Levofloxacin is a newer molecule of third generation fluoroquinolones. It is active L - isomer of ofloxacin having twice antimicrobial activity than parent compound. Currently, it is extensively used (Kamashi *et al.* 2018). Levofloxacin has been demonstrated to stimulate the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Reactive oxygen species are reactive by-products formed by the partial reduction of molecular oxygen. Redox cycling of various chemical substances affects the reactive oxygen species produced by cells during the oxidation process. Fluoroquinolones are known to induce the formation of singlet oxygen and superoxide anion (Rawi *et al.* 2011). However, numbers of pharmacokinetic studies are being undertaken in domestic animals and poultry with a view to adopt this drug in veterinary

medicine as well. Its spectrum of activity and pharmacokinetic properties favor its use in veterinary practice. Pharmacokinetics of levofloxacin have been studied in cow calves and poultry, however, the data on safety of administration of levofloxacin in poultry are lacking. Our aim in the present study is evaluation of safety of levofloxacin following multiple oral dose administration in chicken.

Material and methods

This work is performed for measurement of oxidative parameters SOD activity, and GSH level in blood, liver, kidney and brain. Moreover, MDA level in serum, liver, kidney and brain.

Experimental chicks:

A total number of 90 unsexed one day old Cobb broiler chicks were obtained from the Ismailia-Misr Poultry Company, Ismailia, Egypt. In this experiment, the rations were formulated as starter and grower finisher diets. Council [Bibliography 1994]. Broilers randomly grouped into 3 groups as following: - Control, Levofloxacin therapeutic dose (40 mg / kg / day) and

Levofloxacin High dose (180 mg / kg / day). Broilers are slaughtered in different treatment durations (one day, 3 days and 5 days) 10 birds in each duration.

Levofloxacin: Purchased from MUP Company, tablets 500 mg, Levofloxacin 40 mg /kg /day (therapeutic dose) according to (Al-Sayed *et al.* 2014).the high dose Levofloxacin 180 mg /kg /day (high dose) which is tenth of LD50 according to (Kato *et al.* 1992).

Blood and serum samples: Blood samples were withdrawn from slaughtering and the blood samples was divided into two parts, serum for estimation of MDA and whole blood for estimation of SOD and GSH.

Tissues sample: The broilers were dissected to obtain liver, kidney and brain

tissues for determining SOD, GSH and MDA.

Oxidative markers tests: Determination of SOD activity according (Nishikimi 1972) and GSH level according (Beutler 1963) in blood, liver, kidney and brain.

Determination of MDA level in serum, liver, kidney and brain according (Ohkawa *et al.* 1979). All parameters determined using ready-made kits of Bio Diagnostics reagents, Egypt. All parameters are measured spectrophotometrically.

Statistical analysis: Comparison were carried by means using analysis of variance “F test” (ANOVA) where the appropriate statistical analysis was calculated using least significant difference “LSD”. The level of statistical significance was taken as P<0.05. (Millerand . and Miller 2005)

Results

Blood SOD activity and GSH level and serum MDA level in levofloxacin treated groups

Table (1): Effect of Levofloxacin therapeutic and high dose administration for one, three and five days on oxidative markers blood:

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence			
Group (n=10)	blood SOD U/g Hb	blood GSH mg/ dl	Serum MDA nmol/ml
Control 1st day	0.975±0.18a	55.17±5.51a	12.4±1.40c
Levo therapeutic dose 1st day	0.953±0.15a	52.97±4.45ab	13.47±1.55c
Levo high dose 1st day	0.931±0.16a	43.5±4.45bc	12.28±1.40c
Control 3 days	0.959±0.17a	55.72±5.80a	11.64±1.57c
Levo therapeutic dose 3 days	0.475±0.09b	47.51±4.10abc	19.32±1.71b
Levo high dose 3 days	0.2023±0.04bc	28.59±2.66d	23.08±1.31ab
Control 5 days	0.945±0.18a	55.07±6.12a	12.29±1.69c
Levo therapeutic dose 5 days	0.1906±0.05bc	37.88±3.91cd	22.63±2.28ab
Levo high dose 5 days	0.08135±0.01c	16±1.97e	25.56±1.99a

values expressed as Mean± SE. values with different letters in the same column are significantly different.

Liver SOD activity and GSH level and MDA level in levofloxacin treated groups

Table (2): Effect of Levofloxacin therapeutic and high dose administration for one, three and five days on Oxidative markers in liver.

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence			
Group (n=10)	liver SOD U/gm tissue	liver GSH mg/g tissue	liver MDA nmol/g
Control 1st day	1.37±0.17a	2600±265.56a	109.55±9.70c

Levo therapeutic dose 1st day	1.389±0.17a	2594±283.21a	118.8±5.12c
Levo high dose 1st day	1.369±0.18a	2224±168.51ab	120.625±0.79c
Control 3 days	1.409±0.17a	2570±263.48a	108.75±9.94c
Levo therapeutic dose 3 days	1.059±0.13ab	2354±195.34ab	172.3±20.87b
Levo high dose 3 days	0.69±0.11bc	1450±129.31cd	213±19.15ab
Control 5 days	1.399±0.17a	2624±264.23a	108.65±9.64c
Levo therapeutic dose 5 days	0.83±0.09bc	1830±170.58bc	201.1±19.42b
Levo high dose 5 days	0.51±0.08c	910±82.26d	245±23.49a

values expressed as Mean± SE. values with different letters in the same column are significantly different.

Kidney SOD activity and GSH level and MDA level in levofloxacin treated groups

Table (3): Effect of Levofloxacin therapeutic and high dose administration for one, three and five days on **Oxidative markers in kidney.**

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence			
Group (n=10)	kidney SOD U/gm tissue	Kidney GSH U/gm tissue	Kidney MDA nmol/g
Control 1st day	0.4742±0.08ab	340.3±30.42a	52.25±4.67c
Levo therapeutic dose 1st day	0.4693±0.08ab	335.3±28.20a	56.85±3.15c
Levo high dose 1st day	0.4693±0.08ab	281.1±20.32a	59.85±3.79c
Control 3 days	0.4843±0.07a	336.3±28.59a	52.75±4.98c
Levo therapeutic dose 3 days	0.3112±0.03bc	291.3±27.49a	86±7.92b
Levo high dose 3 days	0.2563±0.03c	202±14.67b	100.5±6.85ab
Control 5 days	0.4893±0.07a	339.5±30.02a	53.05±4.71c
Levo therapeutic dose 5 days	0.2562±0.03c	207±18.92b	86.5±5.17b
Levo high dose 5 days	0.1688±0.02c	142±10.41b	108.5±6.06a

Values expressed as Mean± SE. values with different letters in the same column are significantly different

Brain SOD activity and GSH level and MDA level in levofloxacin treated groups

Table (4): Effect of Levofloxacin therapeutic and high dose administration for one, three and five days on **Oxidative markers in brain.**

Grouping Information Using the Fisher LSD Method and 95% Confidence			
Group (n=10)	Brain SOD U/gm tissue	Brain GSH mg/g tissue	Brain MDA nmol/g
Control 1st day	0.2515±0.02a	316.3±19.87a	226.8±15.62e
Levo therapeutic dose 1st day	0.2415±0.02a	311.5±17.88a	240.2±16.11e
Levo high dose 1st day	0.2335±0.02a	311.5±17.88a	255.3±14.40ed
Control 3 days	0.2522±0.02a	316.7±20.34a	229.6±15.18e
Levo therapeutic dose 3 days	0.1434±0.01b	271.7±13.99a	295±19.56cd
Levo high dose 3 days	0.0893±0.01c	188±14.82b	359±15.81b
Control 5 days	0.2485±0.02a	317.4±20.13a	227.4±15.39e
Levo therapeutic dose 5 days	0.1038±0.01bc	200±17.45b	332±14.89bc
Levo high dose 5 days	0.0843±0.01c	154±9.45b	423±28.05a

values expressed as Mean± SE. values with different letters are significantly different.

Discussion:

Levofloxacin, an oral fluoroquinolone antibacterial agent, is the optical L-(-) isomer of ofloxacin. In vitro it is generally

twice as potent as ofloxacin. Levofloxacin is active against most aerobic Gram-positive and Gram-negative organisms and demonstrates moderate activity against

anaerobes. Drug penetration into body tissues and fluids is rapid and widespread after oral administration. **Rawi et al. [Bibliography 2011]** stated that the mode of action of Levofloxacin are known to induce cell death through the introduction of double-stranded DNA breaks following arrest of topoisomerase function. The bactericidal action of Levofloxacin promotes the generation of lethal hydroxyl radicals in both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria which known with its high reactivity and short life time. **Kohanski et al. [Bibliography 2010]** Suggested that antibiotic induced hydroxyl radical formation. As shown in table (1) administration of levofloxacin high dose and levofloxacin therapeutic dose treatment for 3 and 5 days showed significant decrease in SOD activity in blood, while levofloxacin showed significant increase in MDA level in blood. These results come in accordance with **Li et al. [Bibliography 2010]** who demonstrated that quinolones can induce intracellular reactive oxygen species production remarkably, decreased SOD enzyme activity and increased lipid peroxidation. Moreover, during exposure to levofloxacin, cells showed increased DNA damage in a concentration-dependent manner. Reduction in SOD enzyme activity could be evidence of lipid peroxidation activity of levofloxacin. These effects of levofloxacin will cause oxidative stress as declared by **Afolabi . and Oyewo [Bibliography 2014]** who stated that the imbalance between intracellular production of free radicals and the cellular defense mechanisms results in increased oxidative stress. One of the manifestations of oxidative damage is lipid peroxidation which has been known to play an important role in the toxicity of many chemical agents. **Khan et al. [Bibliography 2017]** mentioned that lipid peroxidation is a significant determinant of the degree of free radical generation with MDA being one of the products, as well as, an important marker of the process of the oxidative stress induced as a result. Previous studies carried

out by **Afolabi . and Oyewo [Bibliography 2014]** also indicated that oral administration of a high dose of levofloxacin to mice induced modifications of the extracellular matrix, as was observed with collagen, suggesting the production of oxygen-derived reactive species. Moreover **Kaleagasioglu . and Olcay [Bibliography 2012]** noticed another effect of levofloxacin that causes chelation of magnesium and formation of free radical resulting in oxidative stress. **Huang et al. [Bibliography 2008]** showed that the levofloxacin isomer "ofloxacin" caused release of cytochrome c from mitochondria into the cytoplasm and decrease of mitochondrial membrane potential. There for it can be assumed that mitochondria may be one of the sources of free radical formation following ofloxacin exposure. Earlier, **Dickeson et al. [Bibliography 1997]** noticed that Quinolones are metal chelators, and one possible consequence of the chelation of Mg²⁺ and divalent metals can exert inhibition of SOD enzyme activity by metal-chelating property. In addition, some studies have shown that superoxide dismutases (SODs) are metallo-enzymes. The members of SOD family, namely Cu, Zn-SOD, Mn-SOD or the Fe-SOD, are defined by virtue of the metal ions they bind (**Cohen . and Nyska 2002**). As shown in table (1) level of GSH in blood shows that levofloxacin 180 mg (high dose) treatment for 5 days severely affects GSH level among all groups, while other groups of levofloxacin treatment with different periods and doses affect GSH level significantly versus control group. These results come in accordance with **Pal et al. [Bibliography 2016]** who declared that Levofloxacin depletes GSH due to oxidative damage moreover decrease in ascorbate's activity which makes the cell more susceptible to free radicals. Also, these results also reported by **Olayinka et al. [Bibliography 2015]** who declared that levofloxacin therapy, causes formation of reactive oxygen species and deplete GSH level, these results further supported by

decrease in plasma antioxidant status. Results in table (2) revealed that level of SOD in liver showed that administration of levofloxacin high dose treatment for 5 days decreases SOD in liver significantly and these results are agreed with **Pal et al. [Bibliography 2016]** who found that fluoroquinolones display hepatotoxic effect by generation of reactive oxygen species and decreasing SOD activity moreover cellular damage to liver and kidney tissues. Also results in table (2) level of GSH in liver showed significant decrease in levofloxacin high dose for 3 and 5 days treated groups, also administration of levofloxacin therapeutic dose for 3 and 5 days decrease GSH level in liver significantly, these findings come in accordance with **Olayinka et al. [Bibliography 2015]** who found that hepatic intracellular concentration of GSH decreases and that of GSSG increases, the cellular demand for NADPH increases markedly from fluoroquinolones administration. This necessitates an increase in glucose metabolism via the pentose cycle. A deficiency of intracellular NADPH may exacerbate an imbalance between the production and scavenging of free radicals. When rates of free radical production are greater than the scavenging rates, oxidative damage likely occurs in cells and tissues. Results in table (2) of MDA level in liver showed significant increase in both groups treated with levofloxacin high dose and therapeutic dose also in 3 and 5 days of treatment. This agreed with **Afolabi . and Oyewo [Bibliography 2014]** who found that levofloxacin increased hepatic lipid peroxidation as evidenced by the increased production of MDA in this study indicates the involvement of free radical-induced oxidative cell injury in mediating the toxicity and also added that The increase in LDL-cholesterol, total cholesterol, and triglycerides indicates a disorder in the metabolism of lipoproteins and lipid. It has been suggested that cholesterol is a general indicator of the level of lipid in circulation

and the more the lipid, the greater the amount of lipid peroxidation activity and the greater the amount of lipid peroxidation products such as MDA. Increase in the level of lipid peroxidation has been described as a biomarker of tissue damage. On the other hand, these results resembled with **Wan et al. [Bibliography 2014]** who found that ciprofloxacin and levofloxacin even at therapeutic doses increased MDA concentrations in the liver of rats, indicating increased lipid peroxidation. And they observed that a higher increase in MDA concentration was observed in the ciprofloxacin treated groups with significant increase in the 14-day treatment over the 7-day treated group, suggesting a progressive increase in lipid peroxides production with time of exposure. Increased hepatic lipid peroxidation as evidenced by the increased production of MDA, indicates the involvement of free radical induced oxidative cell injury in mediating the toxicity of fluoroquinolones. As shown in table (3) level of SOD in kidney showed significant decrease in both groups treated with levofloxacin high dose and in groups treated with levofloxacin therapeutic dose for 3, 5 days. Moreover, as shown in table (3) level of GSH in kidney showed significant decrease in groups treated with levofloxacin high dose for 3, 5 days and in groups treated with levofloxacin therapeutic dose for 5 days. These results reflected in lipid peroxidation and the level of MDA in kidney which showed significant increase in in groups treated with levofloxacin high dose for 3, 5 days of treatment and also in groups treated with levofloxacin therapeutic dose for same periods as shown in table (3). The study results revealed massive occurrence of oxidative damage in kidney tissues which reflected on increase in creatinine level as shown in table (6) significant increase in groups treated with levofloxacin high dose for 3, 5 days of treatment, as well as significant increase in groups treated with levofloxacin therapeutic dose for 3, 5 days of treatment. This come in accordance with

Afolabi . and Oyewo [Bibliography 2014] who declared that levofloxacin as one of fluoroquinolone antibiotics have been reported to generate reactive oxygen species which may result in oxidative stress and cellular damage to the liver and kidney, which decrease SOD activity and deplete GSH level in a dose dependent manner and increase lipid peroxidation which measured by MDA level. As shown in table (4) level of SOD in brain showed significant decrease in groups treated with levofloxacin high dose for 3, 5 days as well as in groups treated with levofloxacin therapeutic dose for 3, 5 days which is reflected in generation of hydrogen peroxide which affected GSH level in brain as in table (4) and accompanied with significant decrease in groups treated with levofloxacin high dose for 3, 5 days of treatment and in groups treated with levofloxacin therapeutic dose for 5 days. As shown in table (4) level of MDA in brain showed significant increase in groups treated with levofloxacin high dose for 5 days of treatment more than all other groups as well as significant increase in groups treated with levofloxacin therapeutic dose in 3 and 5 days. Concerning SOD activity, GSH and MDA levels in brain of this study, results come in accordance with **Dogan et al. [Bibliography 2018]** who explained that brain tissue has several characteristics that make it susceptible to free radical mediated injury. Brain lipid are highly enriched in polyunsaturated fatty acids, additionally, brain is critically dependent on aerobic metabolism and the mitochondrial respiratory activity is higher than that in many other tissues, increasing the risk of free radical "leak" from the mitochondria. **Tan et al. [Bibliography 2017]** added that brain processes large amounts of O₂ in relatively small mass, and has a high content of substrates available for oxidation in conjunction with low antioxidant activities, making it extremely susceptible to oxidative damage. **Liu et al. [Bibliography 2006]** declared that certain regions of central nervous system (CNS),

such as the hippocampus, may be particularly sensitive to oxidative stress, because of their low endogenous levels of vitamin E. **Gürbay et al. [Bibliography 2007]** recorded that MDA levels in the brain tissues of adult male rats were increased significantly following administration of levofloxacin. This was done along with the significant decrease in ATPase enzyme activity in a dose dependent manner in brain tissues after levofloxacin administration. The redox status (GSH/GSSG) reduced significantly. **Dalhoff [Bibliography 2015]** found that levofloxacin antimicrobial activity is based on the inhibition of bacterial DNA gyrase. However, this drug has also been found to affect mammalian topoisomerase II, especially its mitochondrial isoform. This impairs mitochondrial DNA handling and eventually results in a gradual decrease in mitochondrial DNA content in levofloxacin-treated cells. Also, **Koziel et al. [Bibliography 2010]** stated that, as mitochondrial DNA encodes 13 proteins, all engaged in oxidative phosphorylation, it is obvious that aberrant expression of mitochondrial genes and/or partial depletion of mitochondrial DNA may affect mitochondrial energy metabolism. In fact, disturbance of mitochondrial respiration and ATP synthesis has been postulated to explain the cytotoxic effect of ciprofloxacin which is in a concentration-dependent manner. **Rawi et al. [Bibliography 2011]** found that there is a decrease in hippocampal ATPase activity throughout the experimental periods, post levofloxacin administration in line with the assumption of about the reduction of glutamate uptake and Na⁺ , K⁺ - ATPase activity in rat hippocampus may be mediated via oxidative stress. Another explanation for the fluoroquinolones under investigation related oxidative stress effects via disorders of glucose homeostasis which have been reported in association with fluoroquinolone therapy (**Garber et al. 2009**).

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